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A Basin-Scale Framework to Reconstruct Reservoir Sedimentation: Long-Term Sediment Dynamics in the Ebro Basin

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Abstract

Reservoir sedimentation alters sediment continuity in regulated river basins, affecting both reservoir storage capacity and downstream river and coastal systems. This study presents a basin-scale framework for reconstructing long-term sediment supply and reservoir sedimentation in the Ebro River Basin (Spain) using publicly available erosion datasets, empirical sediment delivery ratios and reservoir sedimentation observations. Three sediment supply datasets (GloSEM, RUSLE2015 and WaTEM/SEDEM) were combined with sediment delivery ratios and reservoir trapping functions to reconstruct sediment continuity patterns across the basin. Model calibration was performed using reservoir sedimentation records covering approximately 95% of the basin area. The framework reproduces the main spatial and temporal patterns of sediment accumulation observed in the basin and allows the definition of plausible sediment supply scenarios. Results indicate that current sediment fluxes at the basin outlet are reduced by more than 90% relative to natural conditions due to reservoir trapping. Most reservoirs experience moderate storage losses, although several reservoirs are projected to undergo severe long-term sedimentation. The proposed approach provides a transferable basin-scale sediment assessment methodology for supporting sediment management under data-limited conditions.

Keywords: reservoir sedimentation; sediment management; sediment trapping; sediment delivery ratio; reservoir storage loss; Ebro basin

1. Introduction

Reservoirs are a cornerstone of modern water management systems, supporting a wide range of human activities including water supply, irrigation, hydropower generation, and flood control. However, the construction and operation of reservoirs fundamentally alter the natural dynamics of river systems, particularly by disrupting sediment transport. The progressive trapping of sediment behind dams leads to a gradual reduction in storage capacity, threatening the long-term functionality of water infrastructure [1]. At the same time, this interruption of sediment flux generates significant downstream impacts, including channel incision, riverbed coarsening, and sediment deficits in deltas and coastal zones. In highly regulated basins, these effects can be substantial, affecting both ecosystem functioning and the long-term sustainability of water infrastructure [2–4].

In this context, there is growing recognition of the need to develop and implement sediment management strategies in reservoirs. International organisations such as the International Commission on Large Dams (ICOLD) and the World Bank have highlighted sedimentation as a critical challenge for water resource management [5–7] and have issued

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guidelines promoting active sediment management measures, including sediment bypassing, flushing, dredging, and coordinated basin-scale interventions [8–11]. The design and evaluation of such strategies require a sound understanding of sediment dynamics at the scale of the river basin, including estimates of past, present, and future sediment supply, as well as the capacity of reservoirs to trap incoming sediment under different operational and hydrological conditions. However, the large spatial and temporal scales involved, together with the scarcity and heterogeneity of sediment observations, often prevent the application of detailed process-based sediment transport models at regional scale. Under these conditions, decision-making frequently relies on simplified sedimentation rates or isolated local studies, limiting the possibility of developing coherent basin-scale sediment management strategies.

A recent study by Panagos et al. [12] assessed the economic impacts of sediment accumulation in European reservoirs using RUSLE-derived erosion estimates combined with sedimentation and cost data. The study highlights the large-scale relevance of reservoir sedimentation in Europe, estimating accumulated volumes exceeding 1 billion m³ and annual management costs of several billion euros. It also demonstrates the potential of simplified data-driven approaches for linking soil erosion and reservoir sedimentation at continental scale, while emphasizing the need for methods capable of reconstructing sediment fluxes and their temporal evolution at basin scale.

There is an increasing availability of global and regional datasets describing different components of the sediment cycle. Products such as GloSEM [13] and RUSLE-based datasets [14] provide spatially explicit estimates of soil erosion at high resolution. Several recent studies have combined RUSLE-derived erosion estimates with sediment delivery ratios (SDR) and simplified routing approaches to approximate sediment delivery and reservoir sedimentation at basin scale [15,16]. In these approaches, reservoir sedimentation is inferred through empirical relationships linking erosion, sediment delivery and trapping efficiency rather than through physically based sediment transport modelling. These studies demonstrate the potential of combining widely available erosion datasets with simplified sediment routing approaches, although they generally rely on single erosion sources and limited calibration against observed reservoir sedimentation data. A recent study by Nistor et al. [17] explores the relationship between soil erosion and reservoir sedimentation by combining RUSLE-based erosion modelling with bathymetric observations of sediment accumulation. The authors estimate spatial patterns of soil erosion using RUSLE within a GIS framework and compare the resulting sediment production with measured sediment volumes at the catchment outlet and within the reservoir. Their results show that RUSLE-derived estimates can reproduce a substantial proportion of observed sediment accumulation (on the order of 70% over multi-decadal timescales), highlighting the usefulness of erosion models for approximating sediment yield. At the same time, the study identifies discrepancies attributed to human interventions, sediment storage and redistribution processes that are not explicitly represented in the model.

Beyond purely erosion-based approaches, sediment flux models incorporate spatial variability in sediment production, connectivity and routing processes, improving the representation of natural sediment continuity within river basins. In this context, the WaTEM/SEDEM model [18,19] extends the RUSLE approach by simulating sediment redistribution along flow pathways using transport–capacity relationships dependent on topography, flow accumulation and land use. This allows the identification of sediment source and deposition areas and provides estimates of sediment delivery to the drainage network rather than gross soil loss alone. Other recent approaches, such as HOTSSED [20], combine erosion estimates with geomorphological and connectivity indicators to identify sediment source hotspots and preferential transfer pathways. While WaTEM/SEDEM focuses on

quantitative sediment routing, HOTSSED adopts a more diagnostic perspective oriented toward identifying critical sediment source areas for management purposes. At a higher level of process representation, hydrosedimentological models such as MGB-SED [21] explicitly couple hydrological and sediment transport processes, simulating sediment generation, transport and deposition through physically based or conceptual routing schemes. Although these models provide more detailed representations of sediment dynamics, their application at large scale is often constrained by high data requirements, calibration complexity and computational demand. In contrast, the present study proposes a simplified basin-scale methodology that combines globally available erosion and sediment-routing datasets with reservoir sedimentation observations to reconstruct reasonable long-term sediment continuity scenarios with scarce data.

An alternative approach consists of coupling multiple process-based models into integrated modelling chains to simulate sediment dynamics and reservoir sedimentation under changing environmental conditions. For example, Mouris et al. [22] combined climate projections, hydrological modelling, soil erosion and sediment transport modules, and a hydro-morphodynamic model to analyse long-term reservoir sedimentation under different climate and land-use scenarios. The study highlights the strong influence of hydro-climatic variability and land-use change on sediment yield and reservoir storage loss, but also illustrates the high data requirements, calibration complexity and computational demand associated with fully integrated modelling chains. Recent studies have also explored the use of machine learning techniques to improve sedimentation prediction in complex systems [23]. These approaches can integrate heterogeneous datasets and capture non-linear relationships between sedimentation drivers, although they generally require large training datasets and may have limited interpretability and extrapolation capability.

In addition to approaches that estimate reservoir sedimentation from soil erosion, a complementary methodology infers catchment-scale sediment yield from observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs. Early studies recognised reservoirs as integrators of sediment production at basin scale, allowing long-term sediment yield and erosion rates to be estimated from reservoir capacity loss [24,25]. A key concept in this approach is trap efficiency (TE), defined as the proportion of incoming sediment retained within a reservoir. Empirical relationships such as the Brune curves relate TE to the capacity–inflow ratio and remain widely used for estimating reservoir sediment retention [26]. As reviewed by Mulu and Dwarakish [27], TE-based methods provide a practical modelling scheme for estimating sediment deposition from relatively simple hydrological and reservoir data, although uncertainties remain due to the influence of reservoir operation, sediment characteristics and temporal changes in storage capacity. These approaches typically use bathymetric surveys or storage-loss assessments to quantify deposited sediment volumes, which are converted into sediment inflow estimates using sediment density and trap-efficiency relationships [28]. Recent studies have shown that reservoir sedimentation surveys can provide reliable estimates of long-term sediment yield when combined with information on sediment density, accumulation period and reservoir characteristics [29]. Such methods have been applied to reconstruct spatial erosion patterns and support reservoir sediment management under data-scarce conditions [30]. However, they generally remain static approaches and do not explicitly reconstruct the spatial and temporal evolution of sediment fluxes at basin scale.

In parallel, datasets on reservoir sedimentation, such as the Global Reservoir Inventory of Lost Storage by Sedimentation [31], compile observations of sediment accumulation across large numbers of reservoirs worldwide. When combined with local data sources, including bathymetric surveys and sediment measurements, these datasets offer a unique opportunity to reconstruct sediment fluxes at basin scale in a way that is consistent with

both process understanding and observed reservoir behaviour [32]. Although these products were not originally conceived for reservoir sediment management, their combined use provides an opportunity to reconstruct large-scale sediment continuity patterns and explore alternative sediment supply scenarios. In this context, the objective is not to reproduce sediment processes in a fully deterministic manner, but to integrate heterogeneous information sources into a consistent modelling scheme capable of supporting basin-scale management decisions.

Building on this opportunity, this study proposes a methodology to reconstruct the evolution of sediment fluxes and reservoir sediment storage at regional scale by integrating multiple existing data sources. The approach does not aim to provide a fully process-based simulation of sediment transport. Instead, it combines available erosion datasets, simplified representations of sediment delivery, and reservoir trapping relationships calibrated against observed sedimentation data. By considering multiple erosion products, the method generates a range of plausible sediment supply scenarios rather than a single deterministic estimate. The proposed framework is applied to the Ebro River Basin, a highly regulated Mediterranean basin where sediment retention in reservoirs has been identified as a key driver of sediment deficit in the Ebro Delta. The results provide new insights into the long-term evolution of sediment storage and demonstrate the potential of this approach as a practical tool to support decision-making in reservoir sediment management. The proposed approach is conceived as a basin-scale sediment assessment methodology aimed at reconstructing realistic long-term sediment dynamics and support sediment management planning under data-limited conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

This section describes the study area, the datasets used and the modelling methodology developed to reconstruct sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation at basin scale. First, the main physical and hydrological characteristics of the Ebro River Basin are presented (Section 2.1). Then, the global datasets used to estimate sediment production and delivery are described (Section 2.2), followed by the local observational data on sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation employed for calibration and validation (Section 2.3). The modelling approach, including the estimation of sediment production, routing and reservoir trapping, is detailed in Section 2.4. Sensitivity and uncertainty analyses are presented in Section 2.5, followed by the calibration procedure used to adjust model parameters in Section 2.6.

2.1. Study Area

The study focuses on the Ebro River Basin, located in northeastern Spain, which is one of the largest river basins in the Mediterranean region (Figure 1). The basin, with a contributing area of 85,134 km², is framed by major mountain ranges, including the Pyrenees to the north, the Iberian System to the southwest, and the Catalan Coastal Range to the east. This complex topography generates strong spatial contrasts in climate, hydrology, and geomorphological processes. These contrasts are also reflected in the basin's climatic and topographic gradients, with mean annual precipitation ranging from less than 300 mm in some semiarid sectors of the central depression to more than 1500 mm in mountain headwaters, and elevations varying from near sea level at the delta to more than 3000 m in the Pyrenees. These gradients contribute to the strong spatial variability of erosion and sediment delivery processes across the basin.

Figure 1. Location and physical setting of the Ebro River Basin (NE Spain), showing topography and the river network.

The geological structure of the basin is highly heterogeneous, comprising resistant lithologies in mountainous areas and more erodible materials, such as marls and sedimentary formations, in the central depression. This variability, combined with marked gradients in precipitation and land use, results in significant differences in erosion rates and sediment production across the basin. The fluvial network is dominated by the Ebro River and its tributaries, which drain a large portion of the northeastern Iberian Peninsula and ultimately discharge into the Mediterranean Sea through the Ebro Delta. This delta constitutes one of the most important coastal systems in the western Mediterranean and is highly dependent on sediment supply from upstream areas.

The average annual natural runoff of the basin is approximately $15.3 \text{ km}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$. Water resources are intensively used to support a wide range of socio-economic activities, including a population of approximately 3.68 million inhabitants, around 780,000 hectares of irrigated agriculture, intensive livestock production, hydropower generation, aquaculture, and recreational uses. The total water demand is estimated at approximately $8 \text{ km}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$. To regulate and store water resources, an extensive system of reservoirs has been developed, particularly during the twentieth century. At present, the basin includes approximately 130 reservoirs with capacities greater than 1 hm^3 , with a total storage capacity of about 8 km^3 [33].

The intensive use of water resources has played an important role in shaping sediment dynamics within the basin. The need to regulate highly variable water resources to support irrigation, urban supply and hydropower production has driven the construction of an extensive reservoir system, which constitutes the main source of sediment discontinuity in the Ebro River network. In parallel, land-management practices associated with agricultural development, soil conservation measures and hydrological-forestry restoration programmes have modified erosion rates and sediment delivery processes in many headwater areas. As a

result, present-day sediment fluxes reflect not only natural geomorphological controls but also the cumulative effects of more than a century of water and land management interventions.

2.2. Available Global Datasets

The modelling framework developed in this study builds on the integration of several widely used global and regional datasets describing sediment production, transport and storage. These datasets provide complementary information on different components of the sediment cascade, including soil erosion, sediment delivery and reservoir sedimentation.

A key source of information on sediment storage is the Global Reservoir Inventory of Lost Storage by Sedimentation (GRILSS), which compiles observations of sediment accumulation and capacity loss for 1369 reservoirs worldwide [31]. GRILSS provides information on reservoir location, capacity, sedimentation rates and, in some cases, temporal evolution, offering a valuable empirical basis for model calibration and validation at regional and global scales.

To estimate sediment production across the basin, three different erosion datasets are used in this study. The first is GloSEM 1.3 (Global Soil Erosion Modelling 1.3), a global dataset providing spatially distributed estimates of soil loss in croplands based on a harmonised implementation of the RUSLE approach [34]. GloSEM combines global datasets on climate, soil properties, topography and land use to generate consistent erosion estimates at high spatial resolution. It has been widely applied in global assessments of soil erosion and in studies analysing the impact of land use and climate change on sediment production [13]. The second dataset corresponds to the RUSLE2015 model for Europe, which provides a high-resolution map of soil erosion by water based on the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation [14]. RUSLE2015 integrates detailed European datasets, including rainfall erosivity, soil erodibility, land cover and topography, and is considered one of the most reliable references for estimating soil erosion at regional scale in Europe. This dataset has been extensively used for policy support, including the assessment of soil conservation measures and the evaluation of agricultural practices under the Common Agricultural Policy [35,36].

In addition to erosion estimates, information on sediment transport and connectivity is incorporated using outputs from the WaTEM/SEDEM model. This model provides spatially distributed estimates of sediment delivery by combining RUSLE-based soil erosion with a transport capacity approach that accounts for topography and land use [37,38]. WaTEM/SEDEM has been widely applied at catchment and regional scales to analyse sediment budgets and to identify source and sink areas within river basins. Although the model primarily represents natural sediment transfer processes, its outputs provide useful information on the potential delivery of sediment from hillslopes to the river network.

A key difference between WaTEM/SEDEM and conventional RUSLE-based datasets is therefore the distinction between gross erosion and net sediment export. Whereas RUSLE represents the potential amount of soil detached by rainfall and runoff, WaTEM/SEDEM accounts for the fraction of this material that is effectively transported through the landscape. However, the model is primarily designed to represent sediment redistribution under natural conditions and does not explicitly simulate fluvial transport processes within river channels or sediment trapping in reservoirs. As a result, its outputs provide a useful intermediate estimate of sediment delivery from hillslopes to the river network, but require additional modelling steps to represent sediment routing and storage in regulated river systems. These components are incorporated subsequently within the sediment continuity workflow developed in this study. The corresponding routing, trapping and calibration procedures are described in the following sections, while the implications of the associated assumptions are discussed in Section 4.

The erosion datasets used in this study were selected from products available through the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) on the basis of their public availability, spatial coverage and relevance for basin-scale sediment assessments. GloSEM and RUSLE2015 were included as alternative RUSLE-based erosion products at global and European scales, respectively, allowing the uncertainty associated with large-scale erosion estimates to be explored. WaTEM/SEDEM was incorporated as a more advanced sediment-delivery product that explicitly accounts for sediment redistribution and connectivity processes within the landscape. Together, these datasets allow the representation of sediment production and transport processes under different modelling assumptions and spatial resolutions. Their combined use provides a range of consistent sediment supply scenarios, which is particularly relevant in the context of large-scale applications where uncertainties in erosion estimates can be significant.

2.3. Local Sediment Data

Local data used in this study include observations of sediment flux in river sections and estimates of sediment accumulation in reservoirs across the Ebro River Basin. The spatial distribution of these data sources is shown in Figure 2, which identifies the main monitoring locations along the river network and the reservoirs within the basin, highlighting those for which information on accumulated sediment volume is available. These datasets provide complementary information on sediment transport and storage processes and form the basis for the calibration and evaluation of the modelling framework.

Figure 2. Location of sediment monitoring sites and reservoirs in the Ebro River Basin.

Observational data on sediment fluxes in the Ebro River Basin were compiled from a wide range of published studies covering different periods, locations and methodological approaches. As highlighted in previous reviews, direct measurements of sediment transport in the basin are relatively scarce, and many published values correspond to reinterpretations or compilations of earlier datasets rather than independent measurement

campaigns. Consequently, the available data are highly heterogeneous in terms of measurement techniques, sampling frequency, spatial coverage and original study objectives, which introduces significant uncertainty but also provides a valuable basis for long-term analysis.

The earliest estimates correspond to late nineteenth and early twentieth century observations, such as those compiled by Gorría and reported by Ibáñez et al. [39]. These measurements were based on a very limited number of samples taken near the river mouth and likely biased towards high-flow conditions, resulting in high sediment load estimates (up to 25 Mt·yr⁻¹) that are generally considered to overestimate average conditions. Subsequent references from the early twentieth century largely reproduce these values without providing additional measurements.

A first systematic dataset is provided by Catalán Lafuente [40], who compiled measurements collected between 1961 and 1963 at several stations within the basin. These data were obtained from monthly sampling campaigns without fixed sampling dates and with limited control of flood events. As a result, peak sediment transport during high-flow periods was likely underrepresented, leading to an underestimation of total sediment flux. Nevertheless, this dataset provides one of the earliest multi-site assessments of sediment transport in the basin, with estimated loads ranging from 0.05 Mt·yr⁻¹ in upstream sections to over 3 Mt·yr⁻¹ in the middle reaches.

Subsequent studies during the 1970s and 1980s combined direct measurements with indirect approaches based on sediment balances in reservoirs. For example, Varela et al. [41] estimated sediment fluxes by comparing sediment loads at the inlet and outlet of the Mequinenza and Ribarroja reservoirs, complemented by bathymetric surveys of reservoir storage. This approach provided estimates of both sediment inflow (around 1.48 Mt·yr⁻¹) and trapping within the reservoirs, although the results are affected by uncertainties associated with low sampling frequency and indirect estimation methods. Similarly, Palanques et al. [42] focused on sediment dynamics in the lower Ebro, although detailed information on sampling strategies is lacking.

A significant number of datasets originate from studies primarily focused on water quality or ecological processes rather than sediment transport. For example, Muñoz and Prat [43] collected monthly surface samples at several locations in the lower Ebro to characterise physico-chemical conditions and biological processes. Sediment concentrations were reported as part of these analyses, but the sampling design was not intended to capture sediment fluxes, and results are presented as averaged values without detailed temporal resolution. These datasets provide useful indicative values but are subject to considerable uncertainty when used to estimate total sediment loads.

More robust and methodologically consistent datasets have been obtained in recent decades through targeted monitoring campaigns. Notably, the work by Guillén and Palanques [44] involved vertical profiling of sediment concentrations and flow velocities at multiple points near the river mouth, including measurements of both suspended and bedload transport. Although based on a limited number of sampling campaigns, these studies provide valuable insights into the vertical distribution of sediment and confirm that suspended load dominates the total sediment flux in the lower Ebro.

A major step forward in data quality is represented by the monitoring campaigns reported by Roura et al. [45] and Vericat and Batalla [46]. These studies implemented high-frequency sampling strategies, including measurements at intervals as short as 12 h and detailed characterisation of vertical concentration profiles. In particular, Vericat and Batalla [46] developed sediment rating curves relating discharge to suspended sediment load based on several hundred samples, allowing for more reliable estimation of annual sediment fluxes. These curves were later used by Batalla and Vericat [47], who confirmed the strong reduction in sediment transport downstream of major reservoirs, with sedi-

ment loads decreasing from values above 2 Mt·yr⁻¹ upstream of Mequinenza to less than 0.5 Mt·yr⁻¹ downstream.

More recent work has further improved temporal resolution through the use of turbidity sensors and continuous monitoring techniques. Tena et al. [48,49] established empirical relationships between turbidity and suspended sediment concentration, enabling the reconstruction of continuous time series of sediment transport. This approach allows for a more accurate representation of sediment flux variability, including the contribution of high-flow events, and yields lower average sediment loads (on the order of 0.1 Mt·yr⁻¹ in the lower Ebro), reflecting the cumulative impact of reservoir trapping and flow regulation.

Table 1 compiles the sediment flux observations used in this study, integrating data from multiple sources and measurement campaigns conducted over the last century. Given the heterogeneity of the available information and the proximity of several sampling locations, observations corresponding to nearby sites have been aggregated into a reduced set of representative points along the river network. This simplification allows for a more consistent comparison with model outputs while preserving the main spatial patterns of sediment transport within the basin. The available sediment flux data can be broadly classified into three groups: (i) early historical estimates with limited methodological information and high uncertainty, (ii) indirect or opportunistic measurements derived from studies with different primary objectives, and (iii) recent targeted monitoring campaigns with improved sampling strategies and higher reliability. Despite their heterogeneity, these datasets provide a consistent picture of the long-term evolution of sediment transport in the basin, characterised by a marked decline in sediment flux associated with reservoir construction and operation. This diversity of data sources is explicitly considered in the present study, both in the calibration of model parameters and in the evaluation of model performance.

Table 1. Summary of observed sediment fluxes in the Ebro River Basin compiled from published studies.

River	Location	Obs. Year	Flow (Mt/yr)	Source
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1901	25	Ibàñez et al. 1996 [39]
Ebro	Miranda de Ebro	1962	0.0502	Catalán 1969 [40]
Ebro	Zaragoza	1962	3.281	Catalán 1969 [40]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1962	2.241	Catalán 1969 [40]
Aragón	Jaca	1962	0.00335	Catalán 1969 [40]
N. Ribargozana	La Piñana	1962	0.01081	Catalán 1969 [40]
Cinca	Fraga	1962	0.745	Catalán 1969 [40]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1962	2.2	Catalán 1969 [40]
Ebro	Escatrón	1976	1.48	Varela et al. 1986 [41]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1976	0.32	Varela et al. 1986 [41]
Ebro	Escatrón	1986	3.49	Palanques et al. 1990 [42]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1986	1.21	Palanques et al. 1990 [42]
Cinca	Fraga	1986	0.64	Palanques et al. 1990 [42]
Segre	Serós	1986	0.26	Palanques et al. 1990 [42]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1986	0.13	Muñoz & Prat 1989 [43]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1989	0.12	Guillén & Palanques 1992 [44]
Ebro	Escatrón	1998	0.76	Roura et al. 2008 [45]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	1998	0.4	Roura et al. 2008 [45]
Ebro	Escatrón	2003	1.64	Vericat & Batalla 2006 [46]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	2003	0.45	Vericat & Batalla 2006 [46]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	2004	0.092	Tena et al. 2011 [48]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	2006	0.22	Batalla & Vericat 2011 [47]
Ebro	Mora de Ebro	2006	0.116	Tena et al. 2011 [48]

The main source of information on sediment accumulation in reservoirs is derived from a large-scale bathymetric survey campaign conducted in Spain during the late twentieth century. This initiative aimed to assess reservoir capacity loss due to sedimentation across multiple river basins. The results of this campaign were compiled and published in a series of technical reports and conference proceedings, among which the work by Avendaño et al. [50] constitutes the primary reference used in this study, complemented by subsequent publications presenting largely overlapping datasets [51].

The methodology adopted in this campaign was based on the comparison between the original reservoir capacity and the capacity measured at the time of the survey. The initial capacity was reconstructed from historical design data, while the updated capacity was obtained through a combination of photogrammetric and bathymetric techniques. Specifically, aerial photogrammetry was used to characterise the emerged portion of the reservoir basin, while submerged areas were surveyed using bathymetric measurements. The integration of both datasets allowed the construction of updated elevation–area–volume curves for each reservoir.

The volume of accumulated sediment was then estimated as the difference between the initial and surveyed storage capacities at the normal water level. This approach provides an integrated measure of sediment deposition over the operational lifetime of each reservoir, typically spanning several decades. In addition, sedimentological analyses were carried out in a subset of reservoirs to characterise sediment texture and estimate bulk density, recognising that sediment composition and compaction influence the relationship between deposited volume and sediment mass [52].

The dataset compiled by Avendaño et al. [50] includes information for more than 100 reservoirs distributed across the main Spanish river basins, including a significant number of reservoirs within the Ebro basin. For each reservoir, the available information typically includes initial and surveyed storage capacity, year of construction and survey, total and annualised capacity loss, and qualitative information on sediment texture. The results indicate that, although most reservoirs exhibit moderate levels of sedimentation, a subset shows significant capacity loss, with approximately 79% of reservoirs experiencing less than 20% loss of storage capacity and only a small fraction exceeding 50%.

Despite its broad spatial coverage and methodological consistency, this dataset is subject to several sources of uncertainty. These include potential inaccuracies in the estimation of initial storage capacity, limitations associated with photogrammetric and bathymetric measurements, and the fact that only a limited number of surveys are available for each reservoir. In particular, capacity variations smaller than approximately 5% may fall within the margin of measurement error. Nevertheless, the dataset provides a unique and coherent basis for estimating long-term sediment accumulation in reservoirs and constitutes a key input for the calibration of the modelling strategy developed in this study.

To complement this regional-scale dataset, more recent and detailed studies have been carried out in the lower Ebro basin, focusing on the Mequinenza and Ribarroja reservoirs [53–56]. These studies combine high-frequency measurements of suspended sediment transport with detailed topographic and bathymetric surveys, providing a more refined characterisation of sediment accumulation processes.

In particular, detailed analyses based on topographic and bathymetric data have provided estimates of the total accumulated sediment volume in both reservoirs. In Mequinenza, comparisons between initial reservoir geometry and recent surveys indicate a total sediment accumulation between 75 and 100 hm³ since the start of operation in the mid-1960s, corresponding to an average rate of approximately 1.5–2 hm³·yr^{−1}. These studies also reveal a highly heterogeneous spatial distribution of sediment deposition, with around 80% of the sediment stored in the upstream reaches of the reservoir, typically

between 45 and 85 km from the dam, where coarse material is deposited under high-flow conditions. In contrast, finer sediments are transported further downstream and deposited progressively along the reservoir, with a smaller fraction accumulating near the dam.

A similar analysis for the Ribarroja reservoir indicates a total accumulated sediment volume of approximately 13 hm³ between the time of construction and the 2007 bathymetric survey, corresponding to an average accumulation rate of about 0.33 hm³·yr⁻¹. As in Mequinenza, the spatial distribution of sediment follows a characteristic pattern, with deposition zones located in the upstream part of the reservoir, transitional zones with near-equilibrium conditions, and renewed accumulation near the dam due to the barrier effect.

These recent studies provide valuable insight into both the magnitude and spatial distribution of sediment accumulation, highlighting the strong influence of hydrological variability and reservoir operation on sediment dynamics. At the same time, the differences between long-term average accumulation rates derived from bathymetric surveys and short-term estimates based on sediment flux measurements underline the importance of temporal variability and the role of extreme events.

Table 2 summarises the information compiled for the main reservoirs considered in this study, including estimates of accumulated sediment volume and associated temporal scales. The dataset comprises 19 reservoirs, representing approximately 15% of the reservoirs included in the basin model. Despite this relatively small number, these reservoirs account for about 3.4 km³ of storage capacity, corresponding to approximately 43% of the total reservoir storage capacity of the Ebro Basin. This dataset provides a key basis for the calibration and validation of the modelling scheme, allowing the comparison between modelled sediment inflows and observed long-term storage within reservoirs.

Table 2. Summary of sediment accumulation data in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin.

Reservoir	Const. Year	Capacity (hm ³)	Bathym. Year	Volume (hm ³)	Source
Mequinenza	1964	1530	1982	92.82	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Mequinenza	1964	1530	2008	133	Tragsatec 2012 [53]
Mequinenza	1964	1530	2012	76.89	Control de Obra Civil 2012 [54]
Mequinenza	1964	1530	2019	206.7	Sánchez-Arcilla et al., 2025 [56]
Yesa	1959	447	1986	20.78	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Mediano	1959	436	1996	12.15	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Talarn	1916	227	1990	69.59	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Ribarroja	1969	207	1982	12.22	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Ribarroja	1969	207	2007	13.1	Dolz & Armengol 2009 [55]
Ribarroja	1969	207	2019	43.08	Sánchez-Arcilla et al., 2025 [56]
La Sotonera	1963	189	1986	7.29	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Oliana	1959	101	2001	14.91	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Barasona	1932	92	1993	24.76	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
La Tranquera	1959	84	1994	0.12	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Alloz	1930	65	1997	17.58	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Santolea	1932	43	1993	1.85	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Cueva Foradada	1926	22	1992	6.62	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Pena	1930	18	1989	3.62	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Santa Maria Belsue	1931	13	1980	1.74	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Moneva	1929	8	1984	0.63	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Las Torcas	1946	7	1979	3.2	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Gallipuéen	1927	4	1979	0.84	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Arguis	1938	3	1980	0.76	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]
Valdabra	1983	3	1998	1.65	Avendaño et al. 1997 [50]

2.4. Methods

The modelling framework developed in this study aims to reconstruct sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation at basin scale by combining available datasets on soil erosion, sediment delivery and reservoir characteristics. The approach is not intended to represent the physical processes of sediment transport explicitly, but rather to provide a consistent, data-driven reconstruction of sediment fluxes compatible with observed sedimentation patterns. The model integrates three main components: (i) estimation of sediment production at subbasin scale, (ii) routing of sediment through the river network under natural conditions, and (iii) simulation of sediment trapping and accumulation in reservoirs under regulated conditions. The analysis is performed over a topological representation of the river basin, discretised into subbasins connected through the drainage network. This simplified conceptual representation involves structural uncertainty and limited process realism, particularly regarding temporal variability, sediment routing and reservoir operation, aspects that are further discussed in Section 4.

Sediment production in each subbasin was estimated from three alternative datasets: GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM. For GloSEM and RUSLE, bulk soil erosion rates ($\text{t}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$) were averaged over each subbasin and converted into total sediment production by multiplying by the corresponding area. To account for the fraction of eroded material that effectively reaches the river network, a sediment delivery ratio was applied. In contrast, WaTEM/SEDEM directly provides estimates of sediment delivery to the fluvial network by explicitly accounting for sediment redistribution processes and therefore does not require an additional SDR correction.

The SDR was derived empirically from the GRILSS database, which provides information on reservoir capacity, sedimentation rates and catchment characteristics for a large number of reservoirs worldwide. For each reservoir, sediment inflow was estimated from observed sedimentation rates corrected by trapping efficiency, while total sediment production in the upstream basin was estimated from the GloSEM erosion dataset. The ratio between these quantities provides an estimate of SDR at basin scale. The resulting SDR estimates were then analysed as a function of drainage area, and empirical SDR–area relationships were derived from the GRILSS dataset to represent the average decrease in sediment delivery with increasing basin size. The use of drainage area as the sole explanatory variable represents a deliberate simplification dictated by the information available in the GRILSS database. Although sediment delivery is influenced by additional factors such as topography, land use, hydrological regime and landscape connectivity, these variables are not consistently available for the large number of reservoirs included in the database. Consequently, the SDR–area relationships should be interpreted as empirical representations of average sediment delivery behaviour at large scales, with part of the variability associated with local controls reflected in the probabilistic approach adopted in this study.

Reservoir trapping efficiency (TE) was estimated as a function of residence time, defined as the ratio between storage capacity and mean annual inflow. An analytical approximation to the median Brune curve [26] proposed by Jothiprakash and Grag [57] was used to relate residence time to trapping efficiency. Sediment inflow to reservoirs was then estimated by correcting observed sedimentation rates by the corresponding trapping efficiency. This step is essential to relate reservoir observations to upstream sediment production and to derive consistent SDR estimates.

A statistical relationship between SDR and catchment area was derived from the GRILSS dataset. Reservoirs with physically inconsistent values ($\text{SDR} > 1$) were excluded from the analysis. The remaining data were sorted by catchment area, and a 30-value moving window approach was applied to analyse the distribution of SDR values within

comparable basin sizes. Given the large dispersion observed in SDR values, reflecting variability in local conditions, a probabilistic approach was adopted instead of a deterministic regression. Percentile values (from 4% to 96%) were extracted from the SDR distributions and used to define a range of representative SDR–area relationships.

These relationships were fitted using a two-parameter equation of the following form:

$$SDR = \frac{1}{1 + aS^b} \quad (1)$$

where *SDR* is the sediment delivery ratio, *S* is the catchment area (km²), and *a* and *b* are empirical fitting coefficients controlling the magnitude and scaling behaviour of the SDR–area relationship, respectively. This formulation ensures physically consistent behaviour, with SDR decreasing as basin size increases. The resulting parameter sets depend on both the selected percentile and the assumed sediment bulk density, reflecting the uncertainty associated with sediment properties and basin-scale processes.

Sediment flux under natural conditions was estimated by combining sediment production and SDR at subbasin scale. For each subbasin, total sediment yield was obtained by multiplying sediment production by the corresponding SDR derived from the empirical relationship. Sediment fluxes along the river network were computed by accumulating contributions from upstream subbasins following the basin topology. At confluences, sediment fluxes from tributaries were summed directly without applying additional SDR corrections. This approach ensures mass conservation and avoids inconsistencies associated with scale-dependent SDR formulations. For WaTEM/SEDEM, sediment fluxes were obtained directly by accumulating the net sediment delivery provided by the model at subbasin scale.

Regulated sediment fluxes were simulated by explicitly accounting for sediment trapping in reservoirs. For each reservoir, an annual sediment balance was computed, in which incoming sediment was partitioned into retained and released fractions based on trapping efficiency. The retained sediment was accumulated within the reservoir, progressively reducing its storage capacity and modifying its trapping efficiency over time. The non-retained fraction was propagated downstream and contributed to sediment flux in downstream reaches. The model was applied sequentially with an annual time step over the period 1901–2025. Reservoirs were incorporated into the simulation in the year of their construction, allowing the progressive representation of river regulation and its impact on sediment transport.

The model provides a comprehensive description of sediment dynamics at basin scale, including:

- time series of sediment flux along all river reaches;
- spatial distribution of sediment fluxes under natural and regulated conditions;
- temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in each reservoir;
- reservoir-scale sediment balances, including inflow, trapping efficiency, retained sediment, outflow and remaining storage capacity.

This information enables the assessment of long-term changes in sediment transport and reservoir sedimentation, providing a consistent approach for supporting sediment management strategies at basin scale.

2.5. Sensitivity and Uncertainty

Due to the large uncertainty associated with sediment production, sediment delivery and reservoir trapping at basin scale, the proposed framework was conceived as a scenario-based approach rather than a deterministic predictive model. The objective of the analysis is therefore not to identify a unique optimal parameter set, but to evaluate the alternative sediment dynamics compatible with the available datasets and observations.

Uncertainty in the model arises from two main sources. The first corresponds to the external uncertainty associated with the sediment production datasets used to force the model. Three independent datasets were considered in parallel: GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM. These datasets are based on different methodological approaches and provide alternative representations of erosion and sediment transport conditions within the basin. The second source corresponds to internal uncertainty associated with model parameters and methodological assumptions. Four factors were analysed: (i) bulk sediment density, used to convert sediment mass into deposited volume; (ii) the SDR percentile employed to define sediment delivery conditions; (iii) the analytical approximation of the Brune trap efficiency curve; and (iv) the size of the moving window used to derive the SDR–area relationship from the GRILSS database.

Sensitivity analyses were performed using a one-at-a-time approach, varying each factor while keeping the remaining parameters fixed at their central values. Bulk sediment density was analysed using values of 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 t·m⁻³. SDR conditions were evaluated using percentiles 40, 50 and 60 of the SDR–area relationship. Reservoir trapping efficiency was analysed using the lower, median and upper Brune curves, corresponding approximately to fine, medium and coarse sediment behaviour. Finally, moving-window sizes of 20, 30 and 40 observations were tested in the derivation of the SDR–area relationships.

Sensitivity was evaluated using basin-scale indicators including sediment flux at the basin outlet, current sediment retention rate, cumulative sediment storage in reservoirs and reservoir storage loss. Additional analyses of temporal sediment accumulation trajectories in representative reservoirs were also performed. Detailed sensitivity results are provided in the Supplementary Material.

The sensitivity analyses showed that the SDR percentile constitutes the most influential model variable, particularly regarding sediment routing and long-term reservoir storage reduction. Bulk sediment density also exerts a significant influence, especially in variables directly related to sediment accumulation and reservoir capacity loss. By contrast, the influence of the Brune trap-efficiency formulation was comparatively moderate within the range of conditions analysed, while the moving-window size used to derive the SDR–area relationship produced only minor variations in the basin-scale indicators.

These results suggest that the empirical SDR relationships remain relatively stable for the range of smoothing conditions considered, and that the median Brune curve provides a reasonable compromise representation of reservoir trapping conditions at basin scale. Consequently, the moving-window size and the Brune formulation were fixed in the subsequent model calibration, using a moving window of 30 observations and the median Brune curve. Model calibration was then performed by adjusting the two most sensitive parameters identified in the analysis: bulk sediment density and SDR percentile. This strategy allows the modelling approach to preserve a limited number of calibration variables while explicitly accounting for the dominant sources of uncertainty affecting basin-scale sediment continuity and reservoir sedimentation estimates.

2.6. Model Calibration

The framework is calibrated using two key parameters: (i) the bulk density of deposited sediment and (ii) the percentile defining the SDR–area relationship. Bulk sediment density is required to convert sediment fluxes, typically expressed in mass units (Mt·yr⁻¹), into accumulated sediment volumes in reservoirs (hm³), which are the primary observable used for model calibration. Neither the GRILSS database nor the available reservoir sedimentation data in the Ebro basin provide direct information on in situ bulk density of deposited sediments. Therefore, this parameter is treated as a calibration variable. Reported values of bulk sediment density in reservoirs typically range between 1.1 and 1.4 t·m⁻³

for consolidated fine-grained deposits, although significantly wider ranges have been documented depending on sediment composition, degree of compaction and depositional environment. To account for this variability and associated uncertainty, a broad range of values between 0.7 and $1.7 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ was considered in this study. This range reflects the variability of sediment composition and compaction conditions reported in the literature, including values for unconsolidated fine sediments and more compacted deposits.

The second calibration parameter is the percentile of the SDR–area relationship. As discussed in Section 2.3, SDR is not uniquely determined by basin area but exhibits substantial variability due to local factors such as topography, drainage density, sediment sources and transport processes. In addition, erosion models such as RUSLE do not account for all sediment production mechanisms, including mass movements or wind erosion, which may contribute to sediment yield in specific environments. To account for this variability, a probabilistic representation of SDR was adopted, allowing SDR values to vary within a range defined by percentile curves derived from the GRILSS dataset. The calibration process explores percentiles between 4% and 96%, representing the lower and upper bounds of observed SDR variability.

To characterise the relationship between SDR and catchment area, an empirical analysis was carried out using the GRILSS dataset. Reservoirs were first sorted according to their contributing drainage area, and a moving window of 30 observations was applied along the ordered dataset. Within each window, the distribution of SDR values was analysed and a set of representative percentiles was computed. This procedure allows capturing the variability of SDR for basins of comparable size while smoothing local irregularities in the dataset.

The resulting percentile values were then plotted against catchment area and fitted using the analytical expression defined in Section 2.3. The fitting procedure was performed independently for each percentile using a least-squares approach. Figure 3 illustrates the resulting SDR–area relationships for a representative bulk sediment density of $1.2 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, which corresponds to the central value of the range considered in this study. Table 3 summarises the fitted parameters of the regression model together with the corresponding root mean square error (RMSE) for each percentile.

Figure 3. Empirical relationships between SDR and catchment area derived from the GRILSS dataset for the percentiles analysed, considering a bulk sediment density of $1.2 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Table 3. Fitted parameters of the SDR–area relationship for selected percentiles, including regression coefficients (a, b) and root mean square error (RMSE) of the fit, obtained for a bulk sediment density of $1.2 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Percentile	a	b	RMSE
4	7.2485	0.5177	0.0043
10	2.0947	0.5478	0.0085
20	1.5545	0.4575	0.0153
30	0.6247	0.5156	0.0223
40	0.4045	0.5001	0.0290
50	0.2857	0.4753	0.0392
60	0.2040	0.4427	0.0540
70	0.1585	0.3921	0.0649
80	0.1035	0.3399	0.0858
90	0.1149	0.1886	0.1297
96	0.0712	0.1383	0.1353

The results show that the selected functional form adequately reproduces the overall shape of the SDR–area relationship, capturing the expected decrease in SDR with increasing basin size. This behaviour is consistent with the progressive increase in sediment storage opportunities and reduced connectivity in larger basins. The percentile range considered in the analysis extends from 4% to 96%, covering almost the entire range of observed SDR values. The extreme tails of the distribution were excluded because percentile estimates become unreliable when computed from moving windows containing a limited number of observations (20 to 40 reservoirs). Therefore, the exclusion of the outer percentiles does not reflect outlier removal, physical filtering criteria or data-quality screening, but rather the limited statistical robustness of extreme percentile estimates.

The observed dispersion reflects the heterogeneous nature of the datasets used to derive the SDR–area relationship. The GRILSS database compiles sedimentation information from reservoirs spanning approximately nine orders of magnitude in drainage area and a similarly wide range of sedimentation rates, obtained using different methodologies and observation periods. After filtering, 1013 reservoirs were retained for comparison with GloSEM estimates. Depending on the assumed sediment bulk density and moving-window size, approximately 15% to 30% of the resulting SDR estimates exceeded unity. These inconsistencies may originate from uncertainties in either GRILSS or GloSEM, but may also reflect local conditions associated with exceptionally high sediment production or delivery. Consequently, some degree of dispersion is expected when combining two large-scale datasets affected by different sources of uncertainty.

As shown in Table 3, RMSE values generally increase with percentile level. However, this behaviour should be interpreted in the context of the rapidly increasing SDR values associated with higher percentiles. For example, for a representative drainage area of 1000 km^2 , the SDR estimated for the 96th percentile is more than two hundred times larger than that corresponding to the 4th percentile. When RMSE values are normalised by the corresponding fitted SDR estimates, the relative fitting error remains comparatively stable and even tends to decrease at higher percentiles. Figure 3 therefore indicates that the fitting procedure successfully captures the central tendency of the SDR–area relationship across the full range of percentiles considered.

The larger uncertainty observed at the highest percentiles is unavoidable and reflects both the intrinsic variability of sediment delivery processes and possible biases in the available datasets. Reservoirs experiencing unusually high sediment loads are more likely to be monitored because of their operational relevance, which may contribute to the observed dispersion in the upper tail of the distribution. These results highlight the limitations of

deterministic representations of SDR and support the adoption of a probabilistic approach. By considering a family of percentile-based relationships rather than a single curve, the model is able to represent the uncertainty associated with sediment delivery processes while preserving the dominant large-scale signal contained in the available observations.

Model calibration was performed by identifying the combination of bulk sediment density and SDR percentile that best reproduces observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs. Given the hierarchical structure of the river network, calibration was carried out sequentially from upstream to downstream reservoirs. First, calibration parameters were adjusted for reservoirs located in headwater subbasins, where sediment inputs are not influenced by upstream regulation. Once parameters were defined for these upstream areas, the calibration procedure was progressively extended downstream, adjusting intermediate subbasins while accounting for upstream contributions already fixed in the model. This sequential approach ensures consistency in sediment routing and avoids compensating errors between upstream and downstream components of the basin. The range of bulk sediment density considered in the calibration (0.7 to $1.7 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) was intentionally selected to encompass the full range of values reported in the literature and to account for uncertainty in the conversion between sediment mass and deposited volume. Although this range is relatively wide, the calibrated values obtained across the basin are concentrated within a much narrower interval, as discussed in Section 3.1, indicating that the available observations provide useful constraints on parameter identifiability. For subbasins lacking direct observational data, parameter values corresponding to the central region of the parameter space were adopted. Specifically, a bulk sediment density of $1.2 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and the median SDR relationship (50th percentile) were used. These values correspond to the central assumptions adopted in the sensitivity analysis and provide an acceptable agreement with the available observations when applied uniformly across the basin. This approach avoids introducing additional spatial variability unsupported by observations while maintaining continuity in model behaviour between calibrated and non-calibrated areas.

Calibration was performed using all available reservoir sedimentation observations without introducing formal weighting factors associated with data source, measurement period or reservoir characteristics. This decision reflects the exploratory and scenario-based nature of the modelling strategy, as well as the heterogeneous origin of the available sedimentation data. Rather than identifying a statistically optimal solution, the calibration procedure seeks parameter combinations capable of reproducing coherent large-scale sediment continuity patterns across the basin. Uncertainty associated with observation quality and temporal representativeness is therefore addressed through the use of multiple sediment datasets, sensitivity analyses and explicit discussion of model limitations.

Model performance was evaluated by comparing simulated and observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs. The calibration objective was defined as the minimisation of the sum of squared differences between observed and modelled accumulated sediment volumes at the time of available bathymetric surveys:

$$\text{Objective function} = \sum_i \left(V_i^{\text{obs}} - V_i^{\text{sim}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where V_i^{obs} and V_i^{sim} are the observed and simulated accumulated sediment volumes for year i , respectively.

This formulation prioritises agreement in long-term sediment storage, which represents the most reliable and integrative observable available at basin scale. The use of accumulated volumes, rather than instantaneous sediment fluxes, reduces sensitivity to short-term variability and measurement uncertainty, and is consistent with the overall objective of reconstructing long-term sediment dynamics.

3. Results

This section presents the main results obtained from the application of the modelling procedure to the Ebro River Basin. First, the calibration of the model parameters is analysed, focusing on the ability of the model to reproduce observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs (Section 3.1). Then, model performance is evaluated through comparison with independent observations of sediment fluxes along the river network (Section 3.2). Subsequently, the range of sediment supply scenarios derived from the different erosion datasets is presented (Section 3.3), highlighting the variability and uncertainty associated with sediment production and delivery. Finally, the implications of these scenarios are analysed in terms of sediment accumulation in reservoirs and the resulting evolution of storage capacity over time (Section 3.4).

3.1. Model Calibration Results

The calibration of the model was performed using sediment accumulation data from reservoirs distributed across most of the Ebro River Basin. The total area subject to calibration amounts to approximately 81,000 km², representing about 95% of the total basin area. This extensive spatial coverage ensures that the calibration captures the main sediment production and transfer processes operating at basin scale.

Figure 4 summarises the spatial distribution of the calibration parameters obtained for the different sediment datasets considered in this study. The figure presents the optimal values of bulk sediment density and SDR percentile derived from the calibration procedure described in Section 2.4, mapped across the Ebro River Basin.

The left column shows the calibrated bulk sediment density, while the right column displays the selected percentile of the SDR–area relationship. Results are presented for the three sediment sources considered: GloSEM (top row), RUSLE (middle row) and WaTEM/SEDEM (bottom row). Since WaTEM/SEDEM directly provides estimates of sediment delivery, the SDR parameter is not applied in this case and therefore no percentile map is shown for this dataset.

The spatial patterns observed in the calibrated parameters reflect both the variability of sediment processes across the basin and the differences between input datasets. Bulk sediment density exhibits relatively consistent values across large parts of the basin, although local variations are evident, particularly in headwater and intermediate subbasins where calibration is constrained by reservoir observations. These variations can be interpreted as compensating effects that reconcile differences between modelled sediment supply and observed sediment accumulation.

A more detailed analysis of the calibration results shows that the SDR percentile exhibits a relatively low dispersion, particularly for the GloSEM and RUSLE datasets. In the case of GloSEM, the area-weighted mean percentile is 49.7, with 62.5% of the calibrated area corresponding to a percentile value of 50 and an additional 23% to a value of 60. For RUSLE, the distribution is even more concentrated, with an area-weighted mean percentile of 69.0 and approximately 85% of the calibrated area corresponding to a percentile of 70. Extreme percentile values, which would indicate a poor match between erosion estimates and observed sedimentation, are limited to a small fraction of the basin. In GloSEM, only 1.8% and 1.4% of the calibrated area correspond to the minimum (4%) and maximum (96%) percentiles, respectively, while in RUSLE about 4.1% of the area reaches the upper percentile and no subbasins fall in the lowest range.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of calibrated model parameters in the Ebro River Basin. The left column shows the optimal bulk sediment density ($t \cdot m^{-3}$), while the right column shows the selected percentile of the SDR–area relationship. Results are presented for GloSEM (top row), RUSLE (middle row) and WaTEM/SEDEM (bottom row).

These results suggest that GloSEM provides a more balanced representation of sediment production relative to observed reservoir sedimentation in the Ebro basin, whereas RUSLE tends to underestimate sediment supply and therefore requires higher SDR percentiles to reproduce observations. Nevertheless, both datasets yield consistent calibration patterns and constitute valuable sources of information for the modelling strategy.

The analysis of bulk sediment density further supports the consistency of the calibration. Area-weighted mean values of $1.31 t \cdot m^{-3}$, $1.13 t \cdot m^{-3}$ and $1.39 t \cdot m^{-3}$ are obtained for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM, respectively, all within the range commonly reported in the literature. The spatial distribution of density values reveals a bimodal pattern for GloSEM and RUSLE. In GloSEM, 62.6% of the calibrated area corresponds to a density of $1.4 t \cdot m^{-3}$ and 22.7% to $1.1 t \cdot m^{-3}$, while in RUSLE 66.5% of the area is associated with $1.3 t \cdot m^{-3}$ and 22.2% with $1.0 t \cdot m^{-3}$. The remaining values represent less than 5% of

the calibrated area. In contrast, WaTEM/SEDEM shows a more concentrated distribution, with 62.5% of the area corresponding to $1.5 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and 20.3% to $1.4 \text{ t}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

These results indicate that the calibration converges towards a relatively narrow region of the parameter space despite the wide ranges initially considered for both SDR percentile and bulk sediment density. The clustering of calibrated SDR percentiles around the central part of the distribution and the convergence of sediment density values towards a limited interval suggest that the available observations provide meaningful constraints on the calibration process. At the same time, this convergence should not be interpreted as an independent validation of the physical realism of the calibrated parameters. Rather, it reflects the ability of the selected parameter combinations to establish consistency between the sediment supply estimated from the erosion datasets and the sediment accumulation observed in reservoirs. The limited dispersion observed in the calibrated parameters has two complementary implications. On the one hand, it suggests that the calibration does not require extreme parameter values over most of the basin, supporting the internal consistency of the modelling strategy. On the other hand, it indicates that uncertainty is represented primarily through the use of alternative sediment-supply datasets and scenario analysis rather than through large spatial variability in the calibrated parameters themselves. It is also possible that part of the observed convergence reflects compensation between the SDR percentile and sediment-density parameters, a common feature of calibration procedures based on integrated sediment-balance observations. Nevertheless, the independent comparison with sediment-flux observations at multiple locations across the basin provides additional support for the plausibility of the reconstructed sediment continuity patterns beyond the reservoirs used for calibration.

Figure 5 presents the temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in the 16 largest reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin for which observational data are available. Each panel compares modelled sediment accumulation derived from the three sediment datasets (GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM) with observed values obtained from bathymetric surveys. In several reservoirs, the trajectories obtained from the different sediment datasets partially overlap, reflecting the convergence of the calibrated simulations towards similar sediment accumulation estimates. The model is able to reproduce the observed sediment accumulation patterns in most reservoirs, both in terms of magnitude and temporal evolution. The agreement is particularly strong for the GloSEM and RUSLE datasets, which provide consistent results in 13 out of the 16 analysed reservoirs. This consistency indicates that, despite differences in the underlying erosion estimates, both datasets lead to similar sediment supply patterns once calibrated within the modelling framework. In the three cases where agreement is not achieved (Alloz, Peña and Santa María de Belsué), RUSLE-based estimates systematically underestimate sediment accumulation. These reservoirs are located in headwater basins with relatively small drainage areas, where local sediment sources and processes, such as mass movements or channel erosion, may not be adequately captured by large-scale erosion models. However, these cases represent a very limited fraction of the study domain, accounting for less than 0.4% of the total calibrated basin area.

Results obtained using WaTEM/SEDEM show a lower level of agreement with observations. In 9 out of the 16 reservoirs, the model is not able to reproduce observed sediment accumulation within the calibration range. In 6 cases, sedimentation is underestimated, while in 3 cases it is overestimated. This behaviour reflects the more constrained nature of WaTEM/SEDEM, which explicitly represents sediment redistribution processes and therefore offers less flexibility during calibration. Despite this lower level of agreement at the reservoir scale, the spatial extent of these discrepancies remains limited. Reservoirs where sedimentation is underestimated correspond to approximately 6% of the calibrated basin area, while overestimation occurs in about 4%. In the remaining 90% of the basin,

the model is able to reproduce observed sediment accumulation using WaTEM/SEDEM-derived inputs.

Figure 5. Temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin. Each panel shows the comparison between observed sediment volumes and modelled accumulation derived from GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets. Reservoirs are arranged according to their storage capacity.

The results demonstrate a strong agreement between modelled and observed sediment accumulation for GloSEM and RUSLE, and a somewhat lower but still acceptable performance for WaTEM/SEDEM. These findings support the use of the three datasets as complementary sources of information to analyse sediment supply and reservoir sedimentation scenarios at basin scale, while highlighting the importance of considering their respective limitations.

3.2. Model Validation

Model validation was carried out using independent observations of sediment flux available at selected locations within the Ebro River Basin. These data were not used during the calibration process and therefore provide an independent basis to evaluate the performance of the modelling framework.

Figure 6 compares simulated sediment fluxes with observations at eight locations distributed across the basin. The figure includes four sites along the main Ebro River and one site in each of the Segre, Cinca, Aragón and Noguera Ribagorzana rivers. Each panel shows the temporal evolution of simulated sediment flux derived from the three datasets (GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM), together with the available observations.

Figure 6. Temporal evolution of sediment flux at selected locations in the Ebro River Basin. Each panel compares observed sediment fluxes with modelled values derived from GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets.

The agreement between simulated and observed sediment fluxes is satisfactory, particularly considering the limited and heterogeneous nature of the observational data. The three datasets produce broadly consistent temporal patterns at most locations, indicating that the model captures the main spatial and temporal trends in sediment transport across the basin. However, discrepancies are observed in some cases, particularly in upstream locations with small contributing areas, such as Miranda de Ebro and the Aragón River at Jaca, where local processes may not be adequately represented by large-scale datasets.

Model results tend to overestimate sediment fluxes in several locations, most notably at Escatrón, upstream of the Mequinenza reservoir. This behaviour may be partly explained by uncertainties in both erosion estimates and observational data, as well as by the limited temporal representativeness of the measurements. It should be noted that the available observations are not based on continuous long-term monitoring, but rather on measurement campaigns with variable sampling strategies and durations, which introduces additional uncertainty in the comparison.

A complementary assessment of model performance is provided in Figure 7, which presents scatter plots of simulated versus observed values for both reservoir sediment accumulation (upper panels) and river sediment flux (lower panels). Detailed results for all reservoirs with observations are provided in Table S1 (Supplementary Material), which reports observations and sediment accumulation estimates for the same year for the three datasets. Results for reservoir sedimentation show a very good agreement, with coefficients of determination (R^2) of 0.97 for GloSEM, 0.96 for RUSLE and 0.90 for WaTEM/SEDEM. This is expected, as reservoir data were used for model calibration. The corresponding PBIAS values are also relatively low for GloSEM (−1.54%) and RUSLE (11.00%), indicating limited systematic bias in the reconstructed sediment accumulation volumes. WaTEM/SEDEM shows a larger negative bias (−86.00%), consistent with the lower flexibility of this dataset within the calibration strategy.

Additional insight into the sequential calibration procedure can be obtained by comparing calibration performance at different levels of the river network. For the 17 headwater reservoirs used in the first stage of the calibration, PBIAS values are 6.05%, 22.87% and −124.16% for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM, respectively. At the second calibration level, represented by the Mequinenza reservoir, the corresponding values decrease substantially to −1.96%, 1.98% and −1.00%. At the downstream Ribarroja reservoir, PBIAS values increase again to −33.27%, −28.14% and −29.63%. However, these estimates are

strongly influenced by the existence of several historical observations that show considerable inconsistencies between successive bathymetric surveys. Overall, the results do not indicate a progressive amplification of calibration errors along the drainage network. On the contrary, the convergence of the three sediment datasets towards very similar estimates in the largest downstream reservoirs suggests that local errors in upstream subbasins tend to compensate when integrated over larger drainage areas. This behaviour supports the robustness of the sequential calibration strategy and indicates that uncertainty propagation remains bounded at basin scale.

Figure 7. Comparison between observed and simulated sediment values in the Ebro River Basin. Upper panels show accumulated sediment volumes in reservoirs, while lower panels show sediment flux in river sections. Results are shown for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM dataset.

In contrast, the agreement for sediment flux in rivers is more limited, with R^2 values of 0.65, 0.50 and 0.49 for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM, respectively. The corresponding PBIAS values are relatively large (-667.68% , -542.14% and -332.89%), indicating that the model generally predicts higher sediment fluxes than those reported in the available observations. This discrepancy is partly explained by the nature of the sediment flux dataset, which is based on sparse historical measurement campaigns of highly variable duration, methodology and representativeness rather than on continuous long-term monitoring records. Consequently, individual observations may reflect local or short-term hydrological conditions that are not directly comparable with the long-term average sediment flux reconstructed by the model. In addition, the calibration procedure was primarily constrained using cumulative reservoir sedimentation data, which integrate sediment transport processes over long periods of time and therefore provide a more stable basis for regional-scale reconstruction.

Model results tend to overestimate sediment flux, particularly for lower observed values. It should be noted that the comparison is performed in logarithmic scale, and regression statistics are strongly influenced by the largest observed value, corresponding to a historical estimate of approximately $25 \text{ Mt}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ reported for the lower Ebro at the

beginning of the twentieth century. This observation lies well above all other available measurements and exerts a strong leverage effect on the regression analysis. To assess its influence, the regression was recalculated excluding this single observation. Under these conditions, the coefficients of determination increase substantially from 0.65, 0.50 and 0.49 to 0.82, 0.79 and 0.77 for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM, respectively. In addition, the slopes of the fitted relationships become greater than unity for all three datasets, indicating a much closer agreement between modelled and observed sediment fluxes over the range covered by the remaining observations. The discrepancy associated with the historical estimate may reflect long-term changes in erosion rates, land use, river regulation and sediment supply that are not represented by present-day erosion datasets. It may also be influenced by differences in measurement techniques and data availability between historical and modern observations. These results suggest that the overall performance of the modelling approach is more robust than indicated by the original regression statistics and confirm that the validation results are strongly conditioned by the inclusion of a single high-leverage historical observation.

The better agreement obtained for reservoir sedimentation should be interpreted in the context of the calibration strategy adopted in this study. Reservoir sediment accumulation records constitute the primary observational dataset used to constrain model parameters and therefore do not provide a fully independent validation of reservoir-scale model performance. Consequently, it is expected that model skill is higher for reservoir sedimentation than for sediment flux observations in rivers, which were not used during calibration. This difference does not necessarily imply that reservoir sedimentation is intrinsically easier to reproduce, but rather reflects the fact that the framework has been specifically calibrated to match long-term sediment accumulation patterns. At the same time, the results highlight an important characteristic of the proposed strategy: it reproduces integrated long-term sediment storage more effectively than dynamic sediment transport processes observed at specific river locations and time periods. Reservoir sedimentation integrates sediment inputs over periods of several decades and is therefore less sensitive to short-term hydrological variability and measurement uncertainty than instantaneous or campaign-based sediment flux observations. The modelling approach could readily be adapted to incorporate sediment-flux observations as additional calibration targets in regions where long-term monitoring networks are available. Similarly, future applications could combine both reservoir sedimentation and sediment-flux datasets within a unified calibration procedure, potentially improving the representation of both long-term storage and riverine sediment transport dynamics.

Despite the inherent uncertainties in both model inputs and observational data, the model shows a consistent ability to reproduce sediment fluxes across multiple locations and time periods. This provides confidence in its capability to represent the spatial distribution and temporal evolution of sediment transport at basin scale, and supports its use for analysing sediment supply and reservoir sedimentation scenarios.

3.3. Sediment Supply Scenarios

The modelling strategy allows the reconstruction of sediment budgets at any point within the river network. Table 4 presents a synthesis of the sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin, including total sediment production, natural sediment flux, present-day sediment flux, annual sediment retention in reservoirs, cumulative sediment storage and associated loss of reservoir capacity. The three datasets considered (GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM) produce consistent but distinct sediment supply scenarios. The reduction in present-day sediment flux relative to natural conditions is very similar for GloSEM and RUSLE, reaching approximately 93%, while slightly lower reductions are

obtained for WaTEM/SEDEM. Differences between datasets are more apparent in terms of reservoir storage impacts. GloSEM produces the highest estimated loss of reservoir capacity (approximately 10%), followed by RUSLE (9%) and WaTEM/SEDEM (6%). These values indicate a moderate level of storage loss, considering that most reservoirs in the basin have been in operation for more than 50 years.

Table 4. Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets.

Variable	GloSEM	RUSLE	WaTEM/SEDEM
Natural sediment production (Mt/yr)	92.69	34.41	-
Natural sediment flow (Mt/yr)	15.00	11.20	10.54
Current sediment flow (Mt/yr)	1.01	0.76	1.33
Reduction %	93.25	93.20	87.37
Sediment retention rate (hm ³ /yr)	11.03	9.36	7.14
Sediment accumulation (hm ³)	837.07	719.47	515.32
Built reservoir capacity (hm ³)	8042	8042	8042
Current available capacity (hm ³)	7205	7323	7527
Reduction %	10.41	8.95	6.41

Figure 8 shows the spatial distribution of sediment flux across the basin under natural conditions and the corresponding reduction under present-day regulated conditions. The left column presents sediment flux expressed as concentration (i.e., sediment load normalised by mean annual runoff) to facilitate comparison across regions with different hydrological regimes. The right column shows the relative reduction in sediment flux due to reservoir trapping.

The three datasets show broadly similar spatial patterns, although some differences can be identified. GloSEM produces higher sediment concentrations overall, followed by RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM. The spatial distribution of sediment supply is relatively consistent between RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM, whereas GloSEM shows a slightly different pattern, with lower concentrations in the right margin of the basin and higher values in the left margin. In contrast, the spatial distribution of sediment flux reduction is largely controlled by the distribution of reservoirs rather than by differences in natural sediment supply. As a result, all three datasets show similar patterns of reduction across the basin.

The total length of the river network represented in the model is approximately 10,650 km, of which about 4550 km (43%) is affected by reservoir regulation and experiences reductions in sediment flux. The magnitude of these reductions is significant. According to GloSEM, sediment flux is reduced by more than 50% along 56% of the regulated river length, compared to 50% for RUSLE and 40% for WaTEM/SEDEM. More severe reductions (>90%) affect approximately 20% of the regulated river network for GloSEM, 7% for RUSLE and 3.5% for WaTEM/SEDEM.

These results highlight the substantial impact of reservoir regulation on sediment transport across the basin, with consistent patterns emerging across different sediment datasets despite differences in absolute sediment supply estimates. The combination of global datasets and basin-scale modelling provides a robust framework to quantify sediment flux reductions and to support the assessment of sediment management strategies.

Figure 8. Spatial distribution of sediment flux and its reduction in the Ebro River Basin. The left column shows natural sediment flux expressed as concentration (sediment load normalised by mean annual runoff), while the right column shows the relative reduction in sediment flux under present-day conditions. Results are presented for GloSEM (top row), RUSLE (middle row) and WaTEM/SEDEM (bottom row).

3.4. Reservoir Storage Evolution

To assess the long-term implications of sediment accumulation, the model was extended to the year 2100 under the assumption that current hydrological and sediment supply conditions remain unchanged. This approach provides a first-order projection of reservoir storage evolution under stationary conditions.

Figure 9 presents the spatial distribution of sediment accumulation in reservoirs expressed as a percentage of storage capacity. The left column shows current conditions (2025), while the right column shows projected conditions for 2100. Detailed results for all reservoirs included in the analysis are provided in Table S2 (Supplementary Material), which reports sediment accumulation for 2025 and 2100 for the three datasets.

Figure 9. Spatial distribution of sediment accumulation in reservoirs expressed as percentage of storage capacity. The left column shows current conditions (2025), while the right column shows projected conditions in 2100. Results are presented for GloSEM (top row), RUSLE (middle row) and WaTEM/SEDEM (bottom row).

The results indicate that most reservoirs experience moderate reductions in storage capacity. The model includes 136 reservoirs with a total storage capacity of 8042 hm³. In 2025, a large proportion of reservoirs still exhibit limited sedimentation impacts. According to the GloSEM scenario, 85 reservoirs (50.7%) show a reduction in capacity lower than 10%, representing a combined storage of 4670 hm³ (58% of total capacity). Comparable figures are obtained for RUSLE, with 69 reservoirs (50.7%) and 4861 hm³ (60.4%), and for WaTEM/SEDEM, with 96 reservoirs (70.6%) and 5560 hm³ (70.3%).

Reservoirs experiencing severe sedimentation (losses greater than 50%) are numerous but correspond to a relatively small fraction of total storage capacity, reflecting the fact that smaller reservoirs tend to fill more rapidly. Under GloSEM, 31 reservoirs (22.8%) fall into this category, but their combined capacity is only 125 hm³ (1.6% of total capacity). Similar

patterns are observed for RUSLE (27 reservoirs, 19.9%, representing 95 hm³ or 1.2%) and WaTEM/SEDEM (14 reservoirs, 10.3%, representing 53 hm³ or 0.7%).

By 2100, the number of reservoirs with limited sedimentation (less than 10% capacity loss) decreases significantly. Under GloSEM, this group is reduced to 54 reservoirs, representing 49.1% of total capacity; for RUSLE, 48 reservoirs (47.7%); and for WaTEM/SEDEM, 85 reservoirs (59.5%). At the same time, reservoirs experiencing severe sedimentation (greater than 50% capacity loss) increase in both number and relative importance. Under GloSEM, 49 reservoirs fall into this category, representing 10.4% of total capacity; for RUSLE, 46 reservoirs (7%); and for WaTEM/SEDEM, 28 reservoirs (3.1%).

To further analyse the evolution of reservoir performance, Figure 10 shows the temporal evolution of storage capacity for the 16 largest reservoirs in the basin (capacity greater than 90 hm³). In each panel, the remaining storage capacity is presented relative to the initial capacity for the three sediment supply scenarios.

Figure 10. Temporal evolution of reservoir storage capacity for the 16 largest reservoirs in the Ebro River Basin. Remaining capacity is expressed as a percentage of initial storage capacity for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM scenarios.

For approximately half of these reservoirs, sedimentation results in relatively minor losses (less than 10% of capacity). However, several reservoirs are projected to experience substantial reductions in storage by the end of the century. The most extreme case is Barasona, where the average loss exceeds 70% of initial capacity. Other reservoirs such as Talarn, Ribarroja and Oliana show projected reductions close to 50%, while Escalles exhibits significant variability between datasets, with average losses exceeding 40%.

Figure 11 presents the corresponding evolution of sediment inflow and outflow for the same set of reservoirs. The figure highlights the diversity of sediment dynamics across the basin and the influence of both upstream regulation and reservoir infilling processes. Different behaviours can be identified depending on reservoir location and

history. In headwater reservoirs such as those in the upper Ebro, Yesa, La Sotonera or Ullívarri, sediment inflows remain relatively stable over time. In contrast, downstream reservoirs such as Mequinenza and especially Ribarroja experience a progressive reduction in sediment inflow due to upstream trapping, resulting in sediment inputs that are much lower than under natural conditions. In other cases, such as Itoiz, Escales or Barasona, reservoir infilling leads to a progressive reduction in trapping efficiency, which in turn increases sediment outflow over time. This dynamic behaviour illustrates the feedback between sediment accumulation and reservoir performance.

Figure 11. Temporal evolution of sediment inflow and outflow for the 16 largest reservoirs in the Ebro River Basin. Solid lines represent natural inflow conditions, while dashed lines represent regulated inflows after reservoir construction. Results are shown for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM scenarios.

The model provides a coherent representation of the historical evolution and future trajectory of reservoir sedimentation in the Ebro basin, highlighting the diversity of responses across reservoirs and offering a useful basis for anticipating future management challenges.

4. Discussion

The results presented in this study provide a comprehensive assessment of sediment dynamics and reservoir sedimentation in the Ebro River Basin based on the integration of global datasets and local observations. This section discusses the performance and robustness of the modelling approach, its implications for sediment management, and the main sources of uncertainty associated with the approach. Particular attention is given to the balance between model simplicity, data availability and applicability at large spatial scales.

4.1. Model Performance and Methodological Framework

The results obtained in this study demonstrate that the proposed modelling strategy is capable of reconstructing sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation patterns at basin scale with a satisfactory level of accuracy. The model shows a strong agreement with observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs and a reasonable performance in reproducing sediment fluxes along the river network, despite the inherent limitations of the available observational data.

It is important to emphasise that the proposed approach is not a physically based model intended to reproduce the detailed mechanisms of erosion, sediment transport and deposition. Instead, it should be understood as a data integration framework designed to combine existing sources of information into a coherent representation of sediment dynamics. In this sense, the model provides an added value to widely available datasets such as GloSEM, RUSLE or WaTEM/SEDEM, extending their applicability beyond their original scope and enabling their use in decision-oriented analyses at basin scale.

One of the key strengths of the approach lies in its ability to integrate heterogeneous data sources into a consistent procedure. By combining global erosion datasets, empirical relationships derived from large-scale databases (GRILSS) and local observations of reservoir sedimentation, the model bridges the gap between data availability and the need for spatially distributed sediment information. This integration allows the reconstruction of sediment dynamics across large spatial and temporal scales, which would be difficult to achieve using more detailed physically based models.

The calibration results highlight the internal consistency of the modelling strategy, although they should not be interpreted in a strictly physical sense. The calibrated parameters, namely the SDR percentile and the bulk sediment density, act primarily as adjustment factors that reconcile differences between erosion estimates provided by global datasets and observed sediment accumulation in reservoirs. While the resulting values fall within physically admissible ranges and exhibit limited dispersion across the basin, their main role is to ensure consistency between input data and observed system behaviour, rather than to provide direct insight into underlying processes.

An additional implication of the calibration process is the existence of multiple plausible combinations of erosion estimates and calibration parameters capable of reproducing similar sediment accumulation patterns. This behaviour reflects a degree of equifinality that is unavoidable in large-scale sediment reconstructions based on heterogeneous information sources. Consequently, the calibrated parameters should not be interpreted as unique physical descriptors of sediment processes, but rather as adjustment factors that reconcile sediment production, delivery and storage within each modelling scenario.

Although calibration data are limited to reservoirs with available bathymetric information, these observations integrate sediment dynamics over large upstream drainage areas and long temporal periods, providing spatially aggregated constraints on basin-scale sediment continuity. The Ebro Basin covers approximately 85,134 km², and sedimentation data are available for 19 reservoirs distributed across different levels of the river network hierarchy. Seventeen of these reservoirs correspond to headwater systems without upstream reservoirs with sediment observations, collectively representing approximately 14,579 km² (17% of the basin area). In addition, the Mequinenza reservoir integrates sediment contributions from a drainage area of 57,145 km² (68% of the basin), including nine calibrated headwater reservoirs upstream. Finally, the Ribarroja reservoir integrates sediment continuity over approximately 80,998 km², representing about 95% of the total basin area. This hierarchical structure provides broad spatial coverage across a wide range of physiographic and regulation conditions within the basin, contributing to the representativeness of the reconstructed sediment scenarios. Nevertheless, uncertainties remain

larger in some small headwater catchments where local sediment processes may not be fully captured by regional-scale datasets.

The comparison between different sediment datasets further supports the robustness of the approach. The use of multiple sources (GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM) allows the definition of alternative sediment supply scenarios that reflect the uncertainty inherent to large-scale erosion modelling. Although the results do not coincide in all cases, they show a high degree of consistency in terms of spatial patterns and overall trends. Differences between datasets should be interpreted as complementary information that helps to characterise the range of plausible sediment dynamics within the basin. In this context, the use of multiple sediment datasets should not be understood as an attempt to identify a single correct representation of sediment production within the basin. Instead, the proposed framework defines a scenario space bounded by alternative sediment supply conditions. The consistency observed between the different datasets in terms of large-scale sediment connectivity and reservoir impacts suggests that the modelling strategy is capable of capturing the dominant regional patterns despite the substantial uncertainty affecting sediment processes at basin scale.

At the same time, the results reveal some limitations associated with the use of large-scale datasets and simplified representations of sediment transport. Model performance tends to decrease in small headwater basins, where local sediment sources and processes, such as landslides, channel erosion or episodic events, may not be adequately captured. In addition, the model shows a tendency to overestimate sediment flux in river sections, particularly for low observed values, reflecting both uncertainties in erosion estimates and the limited temporal representativeness of available measurements. These structural simplifications may also influence the reconstructed basin-scale sediment budgets. Processes such as channel erosion, bank retreat and mass movements can provide additional sediment inputs that are not represented in the erosion datasets and may therefore lead to local underestimation of sediment supply. Conversely, the simplified routing scheme does not explicitly account for temporary storage and attenuation processes within river channels and floodplains, which may result in an overestimation of sediment transfer efficiency in some parts of the network. The net effect of these opposing influences cannot be quantified with the available information, but they should be considered when interpreting the absolute values of sediment flux and sediment retention reported in this study.

Despite these limitations, the overall performance of the model can be considered satisfactory for its intended purpose. Rather than providing precise predictions at specific locations, the modelling scheme is designed to reconstruct the spatial distribution and long-term evolution of sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation at basin scale. In this context, the consistency of results across datasets and the ability to reproduce observed patterns in both reservoirs and river sections demonstrate the suitability of the approach as a decision-support tool.

A key advantage of the proposed methodology is its scalability and transferability to other regions. The model relies primarily on globally available datasets, but its application requires calibration against local observations of reservoir sedimentation, which play a critical role in constraining sediment delivery and storage processes. Where such data are available for a representative portion of the basin, the framework can be effectively adapted to other regions. Furthermore, the modelling scheme is inherently flexible and can be extended to incorporate additional sources of information. Alternative erosion datasets or more advanced sediment transport models could be integrated within the same approach, allowing progressive refinement of the analysis as new data become available. This adaptability reinforces the potential of the approach as a scalable tool for large-scale sediment assessment.

The minimum information required to implement the framework consists of: (i) a spatially distributed estimate of sediment production or erosion, (ii) a representation of the drainage network and reservoir system, and (iii) a set of observations suitable for calibration, such as reservoir sedimentation surveys or sediment-flux measurements. In regions where only limited local information is available, the methodology can be implemented using globally available products such as GloSEM together with the SDR–area relationships derived in this study. Where additional regional or national datasets exist, they can be incorporated as alternative sediment-supply scenarios following the same workflow adopted for the Ebro Basin.

The modelling scheme presented in this study represents a pragmatic balance between physical realism, data availability and computational efficiency. By prioritising consistency with observed sedimentation patterns and explicitly accounting for uncertainty through a multi-scenario approach, it provides a robust basis for analysing sediment dynamics in large river basins and supporting decision-making processes. From this perspective, the proposed approach should be interpreted primarily as a basin-scale information integration and decision-support tool. Its value lies not in reproducing the full physical complexity of erosion and sediment transport processes, but in providing spatially and temporally coherent sediment continuity scenarios using datasets that are already available at regional or global scale.

4.2. Implications for Sediment Management

The results obtained in this study have direct implications for sediment management in regulated river basins. The modelling strategy provides a spatially distributed and temporally explicit representation of sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation, which is essential for supporting decision-making processes in systems where sediment dynamics have been significantly altered by dam construction.

One of the most relevant findings is the magnitude of sediment flux reduction across the basin. The model indicates that current sediment flux at the basin outlet has been reduced by more than 90% compared to natural conditions, a result that is consistent across the different sediment supply scenarios considered. This reduction reflects the cumulative effect of reservoir trapping and highlights the profound alteration of sediment connectivity at basin scale. From a management perspective, such a reduction has important implications for downstream environments, including channel morphology, floodplain dynamics and coastal systems such as the Ebro Delta.

The spatial analysis of sediment flux reduction further shows that this impact is not limited to isolated locations but affects a large fraction of the river network. Approximately 43% of the total river length is influenced by reservoir regulation, with substantial reductions in sediment transport along many reaches. In a significant proportion of regulated rivers, sediment flux reductions exceed 50%, and in some cases more than 90%, indicating near-complete disruption of sediment continuity. These results provide a quantitative basis to identify critical reaches where sediment deficit may have the greatest ecological and geomorphological consequences.

The analysis of reservoir sedimentation reveals a contrasting situation. While sediment trapping has a major impact on downstream sediment supply, the loss of storage capacity at basin scale remains moderate. Most reservoirs retain a large fraction of their original capacity, even after several decades of operation. However, the model also identifies a subset of reservoirs where sedimentation is expected to become a critical issue, particularly in smaller or upstream systems that experience faster infilling. In addition, projections to 2100 indicate a progressive increase in the number of reservoirs affected by significant storage loss, suggesting that sedimentation may become a more relevant constraint in the future.

At first sight, the severe reduction in downstream sediment fluxes may appear inconsistent with the comparatively moderate loss of reservoir storage capacity projected for the basin. However, these indicators describe different aspects of the sediment system. The reduction in sediment continuity reflects the high trapping efficiency of the reservoir network, whereas reservoir storage loss depends on the balance between sediment inflow and the very large storage volumes available in the basin. As a result, substantial reductions in sediment delivery can coexist with relatively slow rates of reservoir capacity loss. It is also important to recognise that river systems progressively adjust to altered sediment regimes. Reservoir construction disrupts natural sediment continuity and modifies sediment availability throughout the drainage network, but fluvial systems do not remain in a permanent state of disequilibrium. Processes such as bed armouring, channel adjustment and changes in sediment transport capacity may lead to new dynamic equilibrium conditions over time. Consequently, the environmental implications of sediment regulation should not be interpreted solely in terms of sediment deficit, but also in terms of the long-term geomorphological adaptation of rivers and downstream depositional environments to modified sediment-supply conditions. The present framework quantifies the magnitude of sediment discontinuity but does not explicitly simulate these subsequent adjustment processes, which remain an important area for future research.

Traditionally, sediment management in reservoirs has been based on estimating average annual sedimentation rates derived from observed cumulative storage loss. These rates are often assumed to be constant over time due to the lack of tools capable of representing the temporal evolution of sediment processes. Furthermore, such approaches provide limited capacity for spatial extrapolation, making it difficult to assess sedimentation in reservoirs where observational data are not available. In this context, the modelling scheme presented in this study offers a significant advancement by enabling a combined spatial and temporal analysis of sediment dynamics. By integrating available data sources, the model allows reconstructing past sediment evolution, analysing present conditions and projecting future trends across the entire basin. This capability is particularly valuable for sediment management planning, as it supports the identification of where and when intervention may be required, anticipates potential problems and provides a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of different management strategies.

The results also highlight the diversity of sedimentation dynamics among reservoirs. Some systems show relatively stable sediment inputs over time, while others are strongly influenced by upstream regulation, leading to reduced sediment inflow. In other cases, reservoir infilling itself modifies sediment dynamics by reducing trapping efficiency and increasing sediment outflow. This diversity underscores the need for site-specific management strategies, as a uniform approach is unlikely to be effective across all reservoirs. In this context, the modelling strategy provides a useful tool for prioritising management actions. By identifying reservoirs with high rates of capacity loss or river reaches with severe sediment deficit, the model can support the selection of targeted interventions, such as sediment flushing, dredging, bypass systems or sediment augmentation downstream. Moreover, the ability to reconstruct past sediment dynamics and project future trends allows evaluating the long-term effectiveness of different management strategies.

Another relevant aspect is the use of multiple sediment supply scenarios. The differences between GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM results provide an indication of the uncertainty associated with sediment supply estimates. Rather than relying on a single prediction, the model offers a range of reasonable outcomes that can be used to support risk-informed decision-making. This is particularly important in sediment management, where uncertainties are inherently high and decisions often involve long-term planning horizons.

The proposed approach contributes to bridging the gap between available data and the information required for sediment management at basin scale. By providing a consistent and spatially explicit representation of sediment fluxes, it supports a more informed assessment of sediment-related pressures and helps to identify priorities for intervention in regulated river systems.

Beyond providing a basin-scale diagnosis of sediment continuity, the framework can support the design and prioritisation of sediment-management strategies. The results make it possible to identify reservoirs where sediment accumulation is projected to become a significant operational concern, allowing monitoring programmes and sediment-management measures to be prioritised according to their expected long-term impact. Examples identified in the present study include reservoirs such as Barasona, Talarn, Oliana, Ribarroja and Escalles, where projected storage losses are substantially higher than the basin average.

The modelling approach also provides spatially explicit information on sediment discontinuity throughout the river network, enabling the identification of reaches where sediment deficits are most pronounced and where actions aimed at restoring sediment continuity may provide the greatest benefits. Furthermore, the projected evolution of reservoir storage capacity can be incorporated into broader water-resource planning processes by assessing the long-term implications of sedimentation for water availability, flood regulation and hydropower production. In this sense, the proposed methodology should be understood as a practical decision-support tool for the development of sediment-management plans at the scale of large regulated river basins.

4.3. Uncertainty and Limitations

The modelling scheme presented in this study is subject to several sources of uncertainty that should be considered when interpreting the results. These uncertainties arise from the input datasets, the structure of the model and the limited availability of observational data for calibration and validation.

A first source of uncertainty is related to the estimation of sediment production. The erosion datasets used in this study (GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM) are based on simplified representations of erosion processes and do not capture all relevant mechanisms, such as mass movements, channel erosion or wind-driven transport. In addition, they are typically derived from static representations of land use and climatic conditions, which may not reflect long-term changes over the study period. The differences observed between the sediment supply scenarios highlight the magnitude of this uncertainty and justify the use of multiple datasets to define a range of realistic conditions.

A second important source of uncertainty is associated with the estimation of sediment delivery. The use of an empirical SDR–area relationship, even when defined in probabilistic terms, represents a simplification of complex sediment connectivity processes that depend on local factors such as topography, drainage density, land use and hydrological variability. Although the probabilistic approach adopted in this study allows capturing part of this variability, it does not explicitly represent the spatial structure of sediment pathways within the basin.

The calibration process introduces an additional level of uncertainty. The bulk sediment density, which is required to convert between sediment mass and volume, is not directly measured in most cases and must be treated as a calibration parameter. Although the values obtained fall within ranges reported in the literature, their spatial variability and temporal evolution are not explicitly represented. Similarly, the SDR percentile acts as an adjustment factor rather than a directly observable quantity, which limits its physical interpretability.

An additional limitation arises from the assumption of long-term stationarity adopted throughout the modelling strategy. Sediment production rates, sediment delivery processes

and reservoir operating conditions are assumed to remain constant from year to year, and the model does not explicitly represent interannual variability, extreme events, land-use changes or long-term shifts in climate conditions. Consequently, the reconstructed trajectories should be interpreted as indicative long-term trends conditioned by present-day sediment supply estimates rather than as forecasts of future sediment dynamics. Future applications could incorporate time-varying erosion scenarios, climate projections or changing reservoir operating rules to explore the sensitivity of sediment continuity to evolving environmental conditions.

A further simplification concerns sediment routing within the river network. Sediment transfer is represented through the accumulation of upstream contributions and reservoir trapping processes, without explicitly accounting for channel-scale storage, floodplain deposition, remobilisation of previously stored sediments or other attenuation mechanisms operating along river corridors. These processes can be important at local scale and may influence the timing and magnitude of sediment transfer between subbasins. However, incorporating such processes consistently at basin scale would require detailed geomorphological and monitoring information that is generally unavailable over large regions. The adopted routing scheme should therefore be understood as a first-order representation of sediment continuity designed to preserve the dominant large-scale sediment balance while maintaining applicability under data scarcity.

The representation of reservoir trapping constitutes another important simplification of the modelling scheme. Sediment retention is estimated using empirical Brune relationships, which relate trapping efficiency to the capacity-inflow ratio. In reality, sediment retention is also influenced by reservoir operation, water-level fluctuations, outlet configuration, sediment characteristics and reservoir morphology. These factors are not explicitly represented in the present approach because the required information is generally unavailable at basin scale. Consequently, the adopted formulation should be understood as a first-order approximation intended to provide a consistent representation of sediment trapping across a large number of reservoirs rather than a detailed simulation of reservoir hydrodynamics and sedimentation processes. The model relies on an analytical approximation of the Brune curve using its median formulation, which implicitly assumes average trapping conditions. However, trapping efficiency may vary depending on sediment characteristics, particularly grain size distribution, which is not explicitly represented in the model. In this context, the calibrated bulk density may partially reflect differences in sediment composition, although this relationship is indirect and not explicitly modelled.

In addition, the model assumes that reservoirs operate at or near their maximum storage capacity, which leads to a potential overestimation of sediment trapping efficiency. In practice, reservoir storage varies over time due to operational rules, water demand and hydrological variability. Lower water levels imply shorter residence times and, consequently, reduced trapping efficiency. This effect is not explicitly represented and may introduce a bias in the estimation of sediment retention.

Another limitation of the current approach is that reservoirs are treated as passive sediment traps. The model explicitly represents sediment capture and accumulation but does not incorporate sediment removal processes associated with reservoir operation or sediment management practices. In reality, some reservoirs may release part of the accumulated sediment through low-level outlets during flood events, while others are subject to active sediment management measures such as flushing, dredging or sediment bypass operations. For example, in the Ebro Basin, sediment evacuation occurs naturally in some reservoirs due to the configuration of the outlet structures, whereas controlled sediment flushing has been implemented in others. As a consequence, the model may overestimate long-term sediment accumulation and reservoir storage loss in systems where sediment

removal processes are significant. Future developments could incorporate reservoir-specific sediment management modules or correction factors to account for these operations and provide a more realistic representation of reservoir sediment dynamics.

Another simplification is related to the type of sediment transport considered. The model focuses on suspended sediment load, which is consistent with the formulation of the Brune curve, but does not explicitly account for bedload transport. Since bedload is typically fully retained in reservoirs, its exclusion may lead to an underestimation of total sediment accumulation, particularly in systems where coarse material plays a significant role.

Uncertainty is also associated with the observational data used for model evaluation. Measurements of sediment flux in rivers are scarce, often discontinuous and derived from campaigns with varying methodologies and temporal coverage. As a result, they may not fully capture interannual variability or extreme events, which are known to play a significant role in sediment transport. The reservoir sedimentation observations used for calibration originate from bathymetric campaigns of variable temporal coverage, measurement methodology and historical context. Consequently, these observations should not be interpreted as homogeneous statistical samples, but as integrated indicators of long-term sediment behaviour within different sectors of the basin.

Another limitation of the current approach is the simplified temporal representation of sediment processes. The model operates at an annual time scale and assumes stationary conditions within each year, which does not allow capturing intra-annual variability such as seasonal dynamics or the impact of extreme hydrological events. This simplification may be particularly relevant in Mediterranean river basins, where a substantial fraction of long-term sediment transport can be associated with a limited number of high-magnitude flood events. As a result, the model cannot reproduce the episodic nature of sediment delivery, the temporal clustering of sediment inputs, or the abrupt changes in sediment connectivity that may occur during extreme floods. The annual time-step approach implicitly assumes that sediment production, transport and trapping processes can be represented by their long-term average behaviour. While this assumption is appropriate for reconstructing basin-scale sediment balances over multi-decadal periods, it may smooth the effects of exceptional events and therefore underestimate temporal variability in sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation rates. In particular, reservoirs that receive a significant proportion of their sediment load during infrequent but intense floods may experience sedimentation trajectories that differ from those reconstructed by the model. Future developments could address this limitation by incorporating event-based or seasonal sediment-routing components where sufficiently detailed hydrological and sediment observations are available.

Despite these limitations, the modelling scheme provides a consistent and scalable approach to reconstruct sediment dynamics at basin scale. Its reliance on globally available datasets makes it particularly suitable for applications in data-scarce regions, although its performance depends on the availability of local information for calibration.

Future developments could focus on several aspects to improve the robustness and applicability of the model. The incorporation of additional erosion datasets or more advanced sediment transport models could help reduce uncertainty in sediment supply estimates. Improved representation of sediment connectivity, for example through the integration of topographic indices or network-based approaches, could enhance the estimation of sediment delivery. The inclusion of temporal variability in forcing data, such as changes in land use, climate or hydrologic regime, would allow extending the model towards scenario analysis under changing environmental conditions.

Further improvements could also be achieved by incorporating additional sources of observational data for calibration. In particular, in basins where long-term and continuous measurements of sediment flux are available, these data could complement reservoir

sedimentation records and provide additional constraints on model parameters. Although such datasets are limited in Spain, they are more common in other regions and could significantly enhance model performance and reliability.

Overall, the proposed approach should be seen as a flexible environment that can evolve as new data and modelling tools become available. Its main strength lies in its ability to integrate diverse sources of information into a coherent representation of sediment processes, providing a useful basis for large-scale assessments and decision-making.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a data-driven framework to reconstruct sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation at basin scale by integrating global erosion datasets with regional observational data. The approach combines simplified representations of sediment production, delivery and reservoir trapping, calibrated against observed sediment accumulation, to provide a consistent reconstruction of long-term sediment dynamics.

The application to the Ebro River Basin demonstrates the capability of the modelling approach to reproduce observed patterns of sediment accumulation in reservoirs and to provide a coherent representation of sediment fluxes across the river network. The results indicate a major alteration of sediment dynamics due to reservoir regulation, with present-day sediment flux at the basin outlet reduced by more than 90% compared to natural conditions. Despite this strong reduction in sediment connectivity, the overall loss of reservoir storage capacity remains moderate at basin scale, although locally significant impacts are identified in several reservoirs. Although the framework was applied to the Ebro River Basin, the proposed methodology is inherently transferable to other regulated basins where reservoir sedimentation data are available. Its reliance on globally accessible erosion datasets and simplified sediment continuity relationships makes it particularly suitable for regional-scale applications and data-limited environments where fully process-based sediment transport modelling is not feasible. A key feature of the proposed approach is the use of multiple erosion datasets to define a range of alternative sediment supply scenarios. The results show that, although these datasets produce different estimates of sediment production, they converge towards consistent patterns of sediment flux reduction and reservoir sedimentation when calibrated against local observations. This multi-scenario approach provides a practical way to account for uncertainty in sediment modelling at large scales. The study also highlights the value of reservoir sedimentation data as an integrative source of information for model calibration. By linking sediment fluxes to observed storage loss, the modelling strategy enables a consistent reconciliation between erosion estimates and long-term sediment accumulation, which is essential for large-scale applications where direct measurements of sediment transport are limited.

Nevertheless, the proposed scheme presents important limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The methodology relies on simplified empirical relationships and spatially aggregated representations of sediment production, delivery and trapping processes, which introduce structural uncertainty and limit the explicit representation of temporal variability, channel processes and reservoir operation dynamics. In addition, the available calibration and validation datasets are heterogeneous in terms of temporal coverage, measurement methodology and spatial representativeness. The results should therefore be interpreted as a range of representative sediment continuity scenarios rather than deterministic forecasts of future sediment dynamics. The use of multiple erosion datasets and sensitivity analyses allows the framework to explicitly represent uncertainty while preserving coherent large-scale sediment patterns relevant for management purposes.

From a management perspective, the proposed approach offers a useful tool to support sediment management strategies in regulated river basins. By providing spatially

distributed and temporally explicit information on sediment fluxes and reservoir sedimentation, the model allows identifying critical areas, anticipating future trends and evaluating the potential impact of management interventions. In contrast to traditional approaches based on static sedimentation rates, the modelling scheme enables a dynamic analysis of sediment processes across both space and time.

Finally, the methodology is inherently scalable and transferable to other regions. Its reliance on globally available datasets, combined with local calibration using reservoir sedimentation data, makes it particularly suitable for application in data-scarce basins. Future developments may further improve the framework by incorporating additional data sources, enhancing the representation of sediment connectivity and extending the analysis to non-stationary conditions driven by climate and land-use change. From a practical perspective, the approach provides a useful basis for identifying reservoirs and river reaches potentially affected by long-term sediment imbalance, prioritizing sediment management actions and exploring future sedimentation trajectories under alternative assumptions. In this sense, the proposed approach contributes to bridging the gap between globally available sediment information and basin-scale decision-making needs.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/w18111379/s1>, Figure S1: Temporal evolution of sediment flow for the reference scenario in selected locations and sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM reference scenario; Figure S2: Temporal evolution of sediment flux in selected locations of the Ebro River for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from bulk sediment density values of 1.1 t m^{-3} , 1.2 t m^{-3} and 1.3 t m^{-3} ; Figure S3: Temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from bulk sediment density values of 1.1 t m^{-3} , 1.2 t m^{-3} and 1.3 t m^{-3} ; Figure S4: Temporal evolution of sediment flux in selected locations of the Ebro River for GloSEM and RUSLE datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from percentile values of 40%, 50% and 60%; Figure S5: Temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin for GloSEM and RUSLE datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from percentile values of 40%, 50% and 60%; Figure S6: Temporal evolution of sediment flux in selected locations of the Ebro River for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from fine, median and coarse Brune curves; Figure S7: Temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin for GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from fine, median and coarse Brune curves; Figure S8: Temporal evolution of sediment flux in selected locations of the Ebro River for GloSEM and RUSLE datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from window size of 20, 30 and 40 observations; Figure S9: Temporal evolution of sediment accumulation in selected reservoirs of the Ebro River Basin for GloSEM and RUSLE datasets. Each panel shows the comparison between results derived from window size of 20, 30 and 40 observations; Figure S10: Relative sensitivity of the main basin-scale sediment indicators to variations in model parameters and methodological assumptions. Results are expressed relative to the central configuration (bulk density = 1.2 t m^{-3} , SDR percentile = 50, median Brune curve and moving-window size = 30 observations). The analysis compares the response of the three sediment supply datasets considered in this study (GloSEM, RUSLE2015 and WaTEM/SEDEM); Table S1: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM, RUSLE and WaTEM/SEDEM reference scenario; Table S2: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM dataset and bulk sediment density values of 1.1 t m^{-3} , 1.2 t m^{-3} and 1.3 t m^{-3} ; Table S3: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from RUSLE dataset and bulk sediment density values

of 1.1 t m^{-3} , 1.2 t m^{-3} and 1.3 t m^{-3} ; Table S4: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from WaTEM/SEDEM dataset and bulk sediment density values of 1.1 t m^{-3} , 1.2 t m^{-3} and 1.3 t m^{-3} ; Table S5: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM dataset and percentiles values of 40%, 50% and 60%; Table S6: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from RUSLE dataset and percentiles values of 40%, 50% and 60%; Table S7: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM dataset and fine, median and coarse Brune curves; Table S8: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from RUSLE dataset and fine, median and coarse Brune curves; Table S9: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from WaTEM/SEDEM dataset and fine, median and coarse Brune curves; Table S10: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from GloSEM dataset and window size of 20, 30 and 40 observations; Table S11: Sediment balance at the outlet of the Ebro River Basin under natural and regulated conditions, derived from RUSLE dataset and window size of 20, 30 and 40 observations; Table S12: Observations and model results for reservoirs; Table S13: Model results in 2025 and 2100 for all reservoirs of the Ebro basin.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

GIS	Geographic Information System
GloSEM	Global Soil Erosion Modelling
GRILSS	Global Reservoir Inventory of Lost Storage by Sedimentation

HOTSED	Hotspots of sediment sources and related dynamics
ICOLD	International Commission on Large Dams
MGB-SED	Large Basin Sediment Model
MUSLE	Modified Universal Soil Loss Equation
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SDR	Sediment delivery ratio
TE	Trap Efficiency
WaTEM/SEDEM	Water and Tillage Erosion Model/Sediment Delivery Model

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